

Sinonasal Schwannoma: A Case Report

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Abstract:

Background: Schwannomas are benign peripheral nerve sheath tumors that may occur throughout the body. They rarely occur in the nasal cavity. Paranasal schwannomas are uncommon lesions, representing less than 4% of all head and neck schwannomas. A rare case of Schwannoma is reported in a 37-year-old female who presented with a history of nasal blockage for six months. The tumor mass was removed successfully without any postoperative complications and there was no recurrence during the 3 month follow up period.

Aim of the Study: To report an unusual presentation of Schwannoma occurring in the nasal cavity.

Materials: A 37-year-old female presented with nasal blockage; more on the right side. Rhinorrhea and headache was reported since 6 months. On examination of the nasal cavity showed pale polypoid mass, insensitive to touch and no bleed on touch. Probe could be passed all around the mass. CT scan revealed mild enhancement of the soft tissue density arising from the roof of the nasal cavity extending anteriorly till axilla of middle turbinate and posteriorly extending till the sphenoid recess. Excision of nasal mass was done by trans nasal endoscopic approach. Bone destruction was not seen. The mass was removed completely and sent for histopathological examination.

Results: S-100 immunostaining was expressed, which is diagnostically significant. There were increased number of mitoses and cellular atypia observed in the HPE slides. The tumour was deep seated rather than superficial which is the case for most PSs.

Conclusions: The prognosis for sinonasal schwannoma is generally favourable. The tumour is believed to be slow-growing and mostly benign in nature. However, considering the significant morbidity associated with tumour growth, reported favourable surgical outcomes and the reported malignant potential of schwannomas. The treatment of choice for sinonasal schwannoma should be complete surgical excision.

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Introduction

Schwannomas are rare, slow-growing benign tumors that arise from Schwann cells, which form the myelin sheath of nerve fibers. Most of them occur in middle-aged adults, with equal gender and race distribution. These tumors could be found throughout the entire body, and tumors in the head and neck region account for 25% to 45% of the cases. Schwannomas arising from the nasal cavity and paranasal sinuses comprised about 4% of all head and neck cases.

The clinical symptoms of sinonasal schwannomas include nasal obstruction, epistaxis, rhinorrhea, anosmia, headache, facial swelling, and others. Complete resection is the treatment of choice, and histology remains the gold standard for its diagnosis.

Immunostaining for S-100 protein is helpful to distinguish schwannomas from inflammatory polyps, inverted papilloma, and other disease entities. Re-

currence after surgery is rare. Schwannomas are benign, encapsulated neurogenic tumours arising from the Schwann cells of the peripheral nerve sheath [1]. They present in diverse cellular varieties despite their origin from a limited variety of their cell origin. [2]

The different types include cellular, cystic, ancient, epitheloid, melanotic, schwannoma with pseudoglandular elements, psammomatous, and plexiform varieties. [3] Among these the plexiform schwannoma (PS) represents 4.3% of all Schwannomas.[4] These lesions are reported from the areas of the head and neck.[5]

Two recent review papers recognized 34 cases of penile schwannomas published in the English literature; the site being very uncommon. [6] Plexiform Schwannomas (PS) are confused with plexiform neurofibromas; Von Recklinghausen's disease which have malignant potential [7]Plexiform schwannomas can occur in the absence of Von Recklinghausen's genotype and malignant transformation has never been described in PS. [8] In 1978 Harkin et al. reported in the literature the earliest 6 cases of plexiform schwannoma which were distinguishable from PS.[9] Majority of the PS lesions are solitary and sporadic whereas multifocality was found to be associated with neurofibromatosis type 2 tumours. [10]Even though PS are considered benign, recurrences are reported with them especially when incomplete excision occurs. [11]23% of the PS are reported in the head and neck region 22% from the upper 22% from lower extremities, and18% from the trunk regions of the body (18%).[12]

Though PS tumours are associated with malignant transformation, plexiform neurofibromas can progress into MPNST and therefore identifying PS is essential due to their different biological behaviour. [13]S-100 immunostaining could be helpful since it is weakly expressed (or even not at all) in MPNSTs whilst PSs exhibit strong expression of the specific protein. [14]

Another important feature in such transformations are the increased number of mitoses and cellular atypia observed in MPNSTs in comparison to PSs; moreover, they are deep seated rather than superficial which is the case for most PSs.[15]

Case report

A 37-year-old female presented with a history of nasal blockage which was more on the right side. Rhinorrhea and headache was reported since 6 months. Other symptoms complained were included recurrent epistaxis, mouth breathing. On examination of the nose revealed right nostrils was filled with pale polypoid mass, insensitive to touch and no bleed on touch.

Probe could be passed all around the mass. CT scan revealed mild enhancement of the soft tissue density arising from the roof of the nasal cavity extending anteriorly up to posterior aspect of axilla of middle turbinate and posteriorly extending till the sphenoid recess.

Excision of nasal mass was done by transnasal endoscopic approach. Bone destruction was not seen. The mass was removed completely and sent for histopathological examination.

Figure 1: Pre-op picture showing nasal mass medial to middle turbinate

Figure 2: CT scan showing nasal mass

Figure 3: Tumor showing hyper and hypocellular zones

Figure 4: Tumor showing nuclear palisading forming verocay bodies

Figure 5: Tumor showing diffuse strong cytoplasmic positive for S100

Figure 6: Post op status of sinonasal schwannoma

Discussion

Schwannoma was first described by Verocay in 1910. [16] It is a tumor that originates from the neuroectodermal Schwann cells of the cranial, peripheral, or autonomic sheaths. Head and neck schwannomas could arise from multiple sites and account for 25% to 45% of all cases. [17] Depending on the location, it is divided into nonvestibular, extra cranial head and neck schwannomas and intracranial acoustic schwannoma. [18] Sinonasal schwannomas are rare and account only for 4% of all head and neck schwannomas. In line with these reports, Heinemann M., Ranft A. et al [19] reported that unilateral nasal symptoms could be attributed to neoplastic diseases (20.6%), inflammatory diseases (68.3%), and anatomic variations (11.1%). Among neoplastic diseases, inverted papilloma (6.3%) was the most common pathologic diagnosis. [20] Schwannoma, ameloblastoma, pleomorphic adenoma, non-Hodgkin lymphoma, and squamous cell carcinoma were the least common findings (1.6%). [21] The origin of nasal schwannomas is hard to determine because of the thin nerve innervation over the nasal cavity. [22] Its nerve attachment is difficult to identify during surgery. Sympathetic, parasympathetic, or sensory nerves are considered as their possible origin. Sympathetic nerves come out from the stellate ganglion and are distributed around the septal blood vessels. Parasympathetic nerves from the sphenopalatine ganglion innervate the septal mucous gland. The sensory nerves in the nasal septum originate from

the branches of the ophthalmic nerve (anterior AND posterior ethmoid nerve) and maxillary nerves (nasopalatine nerve). Olfactory groove schwannomas might arise from the olfactory bulb and nerve. [23] The clinical symptoms of nasal schwannomas are very similar to those of inflammatory sinonasal diseases. Nasal obstruction was the main symptom mentioned by patients.

In our case, the most common symptoms of nasal cavity schwannomas are nasal obstruction, epistaxis, and rhinorrhea. Other symptoms, such as headache, hyposmia, nasal swelling and pain, exophthalmos, diplopia, or facial distortion, were less recorded. [24] For nasal cavity schwannomas, a high-resolution CT scan provides details about the size and extent of tumours. The tumours show mild and patchy enhancement pattern on contrast-enhanced CT scan. [25] Magnetic resonance imaging is superior to CT in differentiating tumours from inflammatory changes and in the evaluation of their extra nasal extensions. Magnetic resonance imaging signals show intermediate signal intensity on T1-weighted images and a variation from intermediate intensity (highly cellular lesion) to heterogeneous high intensity (cystic and stromal lesions) on T2-weighted images. [26] Preoperative images could help in the diagnosis and selection of the proper surgical approach. It is hard to determine the tumour origin purely by images because of the total obstruction of the meatus or multiple sinus involvement. Thus, it is often identified during the operation, as seen in this present patient.

Table 2: Origins of Nasal Schwannomas

Subsites	Case number (%)
Septum	32 (57.1)
Lateral wall	6 (10.7)
Middle turbinate	6 (10.7)
Vestibule	4 (7.1)
Inferior turbinate	4 (7.1)
Middle meatus	4 (7.1)

The treatment for nasal cavity schwannomas is complete surgical excision. Head and neck schwannomas are usually encapsulated; however, some sinonasal schwannomas are not capsulated, making en-bloc tumor resection difficult. [27]The surgical procedure depends on the tumor size, location, and invasion of adjacent structures. The intervention for limited nasal cavity schwannomas usually involves transnasal excision with or without endoscopy. Open surgery is usually reserved for more extensive diseases.

Endoscopic surgery has been mostly reported in the recent 20 years, and it is becoming the most widely used procedure. Even in extensive diseases, no recurrence was reported after endoscopic surgery. Some small anterior tumours were excised with a safe margin without endoscopy. For extensive diseases, open surgery is indicated, which often requires developing and elevating a local flap for a better surgical view. The reported open approaches include lateral rhinotomy, rhinoplasty, Caldwell-Luc or Denker's operation, transpalatal incision, gingivobuccal incision, or midfacial degloving. [28]The recurrence rate of schwannomas after a complete surgery is reported as very low. The present patient was followed up for 3 months and still hasn't shown any signs of recurrence. However, some studies (CW Lee et al), [29] showed cases of regional recurrence have been reported, with all other cases reporting no disease recurrence postoperatively on follow up.

Three cases of malignant histology have been observed, and in all three cases adjuvant postoperative radiotherapy was used.[30]Two of these patients showed no metastasis despite their histology, and remained disease free at 1- and 2-year follow up posttreatment. The other case was a malignant transformation 13 years after the initial diagnosis, which was surgically excised, but recurred regionally. Histology is still the gold standard for its diagnosis because of its atypical clinical symptoms and lack of specific image manifestation. [31]Microscopically, schwannomas present with 2 distinct patterns. Antoni A area has dense spindle cells with a palisading nucleus surrounding an acellular central lesion, referred to as Verocay bodies. On the other hand, Antoni B area shows a loose tissue composed of polymorphic cells separated by an abundant myxoid matrix. Immunohistochemical stains are often employed due to the difficulty in diagnosing it purely based on its morphology. Being positive for the S-100 protein can aid in the diagnosis. Although both schwannomas and neurofibromas are immunoreactive with the S-100 protein, Min and Kim reported that S-100 protein immunostaining was more intense on schwannomas than on neurofibromas. Moreover, Calretinin and CD56 are also highly specific for schwannomas, while CD34

and factor XIII a are more sensitive for neurofibromas.[32]These markers further assist the differential diagnosis. Our case had an intense immunostaining for S-100 protein and negative for CD34, leading to the diagnosis of schwannoma.[33]

Conclusions:

The prognosis for sinonasal schwannoma is generally favourable. The tumour is believed to be slow-growing and mostly benign in nature. However, considering the significant morbidity associated with tumour growth, reported favourable surgical outcomes and the reported malignant potential of schwannomas. The treatment of choice for sinonasal schwannoma should be complete surgical excision. The endoscopic approach should be used whenever possible to minimise postoperative morbidity. The role for radiotherapy is unclear. Current literature suggests long-term follow up for these patients may not be necessary. However, should it show histological features of malignancy, then life-long follow up may be necessary. Furthermore, sinonasal schwannomas demonstrate how distinguishing histology is essential in managing sinonasal tumours in order to avoid unnecessary extensive surgery and/or chemoradiotherapy.

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